

Mapping Research Topics on Loan Loss Provision (LLP) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Loan Loss Provision (LLP) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the LLP ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the LLP ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the LLP ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 137 journal publications regarding the LLP ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the LLP ratio are divided into 10 clusters and 52 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 17 topics around the influence of the LLP ratio and 10 topics about the determinants of the LLP ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around LLP ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Loan Loss Provision (LLP), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Loan Loss Provision (LLP) ratio in banking is very important to maintain financial system stability and overall bank financial performance. This ratio helps banks to estimate possible losses due to customer failure to pay, so that banks can set aside sufficient funds to anticipate possible losses. The development of the use of the LLP ratio in banking has been quite significant in recent years. In general, banks have LLP ratio targets that must be met in accordance with the applicable regulations in each country. Several countries have tightened regulations regarding LLP ratios, forcing banks to increase the amount of funds set aside to anticipate possible losses.

However, on the other hand, using an LLP ratio that is too high can also reduce the bank's ability to provide loans and can affect the bank's overall financial performance. Therefore, banks must strike a balance between meeting LLP ratio targets and providing sufficient loans to customers. In recent years, several banks have begun to use more sophisticated technology and analytical methods to estimate credit risk, so as to optimize the use of the LLP ratio by calculating credit risk more accurately. This more sophisticated technology and analysis method can help banks identify more specific and faster credit risks, so that banks can take quicker and more precise action in managing these risks. Overall, the use of the LLP ratio in banking continues to grow along with developments in regulations and technology, and is very important to maintain financial system stability and overall bank financial performance. Banks must be able to strike a balance between meeting the LLP ratio target and providing sufficient loans to customers, as well as utilizing more sophisticated technology and analytical methods to optimize the use of the LLP ratio.

Several recent studies have been conducted to examine the influence of the LLP ratio on bank financial performance, both directly and indirectly. First, one study shows that a higher LLP ratio can negatively affect a bank's financial performance, because it increases the bank's operational costs and reduces profitability. However,

other research shows that a higher LLP ratio can increase financial system stability and reduce systemic risk. This research also shows that a higher LLP ratio can increase investor confidence in banks and the financial system as a whole. Second, several studies have also been conducted to examine the influence of other factors that can influence the LLP ratio, such as bank size, the quality of bank risk management, and the quality of regulations. These studies can help banks and regulators in developing appropriate policies in managing credit risk and optimizing the use of the LLP ratio. Third, several studies also examine the influence of technology and more sophisticated analytical methods in estimating credit risk on the use of the LLP ratio. This research shows that more sophisticated technology and analytical methods can help banks manage credit risk more accurately and efficiently, so that they can optimize the use of the LLP ratio. Overall, research on the LLP ratio in banking continues to develop along with developments in regulations and technology in the banking industry. This research can help banks and regulators in developing appropriate policies in managing credit risk and optimizing the use of LLP ratios to maintain financial system stability and overall bank financial performance.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around LLP in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding LLP. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research LLP. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the LLP ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Loan Loss Provision (LLP) or also known as loss provision for impairment of financial assets is a reserve established by banks or other financial institutions to anticipate potential losses due to the possibility of uncollectible credit or default by customers. LLPs are necessary because financial institutions lend money to customers with the risk that the customer will not repay the loan, either due to inability or unwillingness. If the customer fails to pay, the bank will suffer financial losses. In this case, the bank will create an LLB reserve, which is a portion of retained earnings to reduce the impact of losses due to bad credit or default. This reserve can be used to cover expected losses due to credit provided to customers experiencing financial difficulties. Regulations governing LLPs vary by country, but the basic principle is that banks must establish sufficient reserves to reduce the risk of losses due to non-performing loans. The amount formed as an LLP is usually determined based on credit risk analysis, previous default history, and economic conditions.

Bibliometric studies are research methods used to measure and analyze the productivity and impact of scientific or academic work. This method uses bibliographic and statistical data to study scientific works in a particular discipline or field, including publications, authors, journals, and citations. Bibliometric studies are carried out using quantitative analysis techniques to measure the quantity and quality of scientific work, as well as to understand patterns and trends in scientific production. Several indicators that are often used in bibliometric studies include number of publications, number of citations, Hirsch index (H-index), and journal impact factor. Bibliometric studies can provide useful information for researchers, educational institutions, and journal publishers. Researchers can use bibliometric studies to measure the impact of their work and discover trends in scholarly

production in their field. Educational institutions can use bibliometric studies to evaluate the performance of faculties and study programs. Journal publishers can use bibliometric studies to evaluate the quality and impact of their journals. However, bibliometric studies also have some limitations and criticisms. Some critics say that bibliometric studies focus only on the number and citations of scientific papers, while other factors such as quality and relevance are not taken into account. In addition, bibliographic data may be incomplete or sometimes inaccurate, which can affect the results of bibliometric analysis.

VOSviewer is free software used to perform network analysis and visualization of bibliometric data. This software was developed by the Eindhoven University of Technology in the Netherlands and can be used to analyze bibliometric data sets, such as citation and co-authority data, as well as other data that can be represented in network form. VOSviewer allows users to analyze networks consisting of elements such as scientific articles, authors, keywords, journals, and institutions. Users can choose a variety of network analysis methods, including co-authority analysis, cluster analysis, and principal component analysis. The software also allows users to create attractive and easy to understand network visualizations. VOSviewer can help researchers and practitioners carry out bibliometric analysis more easily and efficiently. Using VOSviewer, users can identify trends and patterns in bibliometric datasets, gain insight into network structure, and produce visualizations that make it easier to explain analysis results. This software can also help users in making decisions and making policies in the academic and research fields. VOSviewer has a simple and easy to use user interface, so it can be operated by various groups, from students to researchers and practitioners in the academic or industrial fields. The software can be downloaded for free from the official website, and is available in multiple languages, including English, Spanish, German, French, and more.

Studies literature review is a type of study that aims to collect and reanalyze literature that has been published in a particular field. These studies are usually conducted to help identify, evaluate, and synthesize the information available in an area of knowledge, as well as to reveal gaps in research and suggest future research directions. Literature review studies involve collecting and analyzing journal articles, books, and other publications related to a particular topic. In a literature review study, researchers can carry out qualitative or quantitative analysis of the data collected. Qualitative analysis involves reading and synthesizing information from found sources, while quantitative analysis involves using statistical methods to evaluate and synthesize data. Literature study reviews are often used in scientific and academic research to help formulate hypotheses, build theoretical frameworks, and find directions for future research. This study can also be used to develop policy recommendations in certain areas. However, it is important to remember that literature review studies cannot be considered complete research or provide definitive evidence. Literature review studies tend to depend on the quality of the literature selected and the researcher's assessment of the data found. Therefore, literature review studies must be carried out carefully and must consider the weaknesses and limitations of the existing data.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is Loan Loss Provision (LLP). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about LLP in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for Sinta accredited national journals via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and

VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords “ Loan Loss Provision ” and “LLP ” throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding LLP using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around LLP using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around LLP using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion of Scientific Publications regarding Loan Loss Provision (LLP) in Banking Sharia and Conventional

There are 137 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 1988 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1 Journal publication data about LLP by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1988	1	2005	2	2015	6
1994	1	2006	1	2016	9
1996	1	2007	3	2017	12
1997	1	2008	2	2018	9
1998	2	2009	6	2019	14
1999	2	2010	3	2020	13
2001	2	2011	1	2021	15
2002	1	2012	2	2022	14
2003	2	2013	3	2023	3
2004	2	2014	4		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 20 21.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Loan Loss Provision (LLP) in Banking Sharia and Conventional

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Loan Loss Provision (LLP) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 17 influences of LLP on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear risk and the stronger the bank's financial position. LLP affects CAR because LLP is part of the bank's capital reserves. When a bank adds an LLP, the bank's core capital will decrease so that the CAR will also decrease. However, LLPs can also help banks reduce credit risk, which can increase CAR in the long term because the potential for credit losses will be reduced. In this case, LLP has a positive impact on CAR, because it provides protection for banks against potentially detrimental credit risks.

(2) Gross Domestic Product/GDP. LLP basically does not have a direct impact on GDP, but through the role of banks in the economy, LLP can influence GDP. LLP can help banks deal with credit risk, which can reduce the risk of bad credit or default. In the long term, reducing credit risk can improve bank performance and strengthen the bank's financial position, so that banks can provide greater credit to deserving customers. In this case, more easily available credit can help increase investment and production, which in turn can increase GDP. Therefore, LLPs have a positive impact on GDP indirectly through the role of banks in the economy.

(3) Inflation. LP can affect inflation because LLP is a cost incurred by banks to handle credit risk. If LLP increases, the costs incurred by the bank will increase, so that the bank will increase the cost of loans given to customers. This can lead to rising interest rates and increased borrowing costs charged to customers, which can ultimately lead to inflation. However, increasing LLP can also help reduce credit risk, thereby reducing the level of bad debts and the risk of default, which in turn can reduce inflation. Income Smoothing. LLP can have an effect on income smoothing because LLP is used by banks to handle credit risk and create financial reserves. LLPs can help banks disguise fluctuations in revenues and profits by delaying the recognition of losses resulting from credit risk. In the short term, the use of LLPs can help banks create financial reserves and cover fluctuations in income and profits resulting from credit risks. However, excessive use of LLP in the long term can endanger the bank's financial stability, so LLP should be used in a balanced and wise manner. Therefore, the effect of LLP on income smoothing depends on the bank's financial strategy and management.

(4) Crisis. LLPs can influence crises in the banking sector because reserves generated from LLPs can help banks overcome credit risks and avoid greater losses. However, excessive use of LLPs can worsen the crisis in the banking sector because it can reduce bank capital adequacy and reduce bank financial performance. Therefore, banks must use LLP wisely and in accordance with the credit risk conditions they face.

(5) Non Performing Loans/NPL. LLP can have an effect on NPL because LLP is a financial reserve created by banks to handle credit risk and avoid NPL. If the bank creates sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank will have enough reserves to handle problem loans and avoid NPLs. However, if the bank does not create sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not have enough reserves to handle credit risk and NPLs may increase. Therefore, LLPs can help banks reduce NPLs by creating sufficient reserves to handle credit risks. However, it is important for banks to use LLP wisely and in accordance with the credit risk conditions they face to avoid excessive use and worsening the crisis in the banking sector.

(6) Non Performing Financing/NPF. LLP can affect NPF because LLP is used by banks to handle credit risk and create financial reserves. If the bank creates

sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank will have enough reserves to handle problematic financing and avoid NPF. However, if the bank does not create sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not have enough reserves to handle credit risk and the NPF may increase. Therefore, LLP can help banks reduce NPF by creating sufficient reserves to handle credit risk in financing. However, it is important for banks to use LLP wisely and in accordance with the credit risk conditions they face to avoid excessive use and worsening the crisis in the banking sector.

(7) Mudharabah Financing. LLP can influence Mudharabah Financing because LLP is used by banks to handle credit risk and create financial reserves. If the bank creates sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank will have sufficient reserves to handle credit risks in Mudharabah financing and obtain profits from the financing. However, if the bank does not create sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not have enough reserves to handle the credit risk on Mudharabah financing and the bank may experience losses. Therefore, LLP can help banks improve the performance of Mudharabah financing by creating sufficient reserves to handle credit risks in such financing. However, it is important for banks to use LLP wisely and in accordance with the credit risk conditions they face to avoid excessive use and worsening the crisis in the banking sector.

(8) Income before tax. LLP can affect banking income before tax because LLP is an expense that must be borne by the bank. LLP is a financial reserve created by a bank to handle credit risk and avoid larger losses in the future. When banks create reserves through LLP, these expenses will reduce the bank's pre-tax income. However, reserves through LLPs can also help banks reduce credit risk and improve future financial performance. Therefore, the impact of LLP on pre-tax income in banking depends on the amount of reserves created and the wise use of these reserves.

(9) Non-interest income. LLP can influence non-interest income in banking because reserves through LLP can be used to handle credit risk and improve future financial performance. If the bank has sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank can handle credit risks better and improve financial performance in the future. This can increase non-interest income for banks because banks can attract more customers and earn more fees and commissions. However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not be able to handle credit risks well and the bank's financial performance may decline. This can affect the bank's non-interest income because the bank can lose customers and fees/commissions. Therefore, the impact of LLP on non-interest income in banking depends on the wise use of reserves and the credit risk conditions faced by the bank.

(10) Price/Earnings to Growth/PEG Ratio. LLP can affect the PEG Ratio in banking because LLP can affect company profits. If the bank has sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank can handle credit risks better and improve financial performance in the future. This can increase company profits and the PEG Ratio at the bank. However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not be able to handle credit risks well and the bank's financial performance may decline. This can affect company profits and the PEG Ratio at the bank. Therefore, the influence of LLP on the PEG Ratio in banking depends on the wise use of reserves and the credit risk conditions faced by the bank.

(11) Risk. LLP can also influence risks in banking. LLP is a financial reserve created by a bank to handle credit risk and avoid larger losses in the future. By creating reserves through LLP, banks can reduce the credit risk they face. However, unwise use of LLP can increase risks in banking. If banks create inadequate reserves through LLPs, then banks may not be able to handle credit risks well and credit risks may increase. Therefore, the impact of LLP on risk in banking depends on the amount of reserves created and the wise use of these reserves. Banks need to ensure that

reserves through LLPs are sufficient to handle the credit risks they face and avoid unnecessary credit risks.

(12) Return On Assets/ROA. LLP can affect ROA in banking because LLP is a reserve created by banks to handle credit risk and avoid larger losses in the future. If the bank has sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank can handle credit risks better and improve financial performance in the future. This can increase ROA at the bank. However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not be able to handle credit risks well and the bank's financial performance may decline. This can affect the bank's ROA. Therefore, the influence of LLP on ROA in banking depends on the wise use of reserves and the credit risk conditions faced by the bank.

(13) Return On Equity/ROE. LLP can affect ROE in banking because LLP affects company profits. If the bank has sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank can handle credit risks better and improve financial performance in the future. This can increase company profits and ROE at the bank. However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not be able to handle credit risks well and the bank's financial performance may decline. This can affect company profits and ROE at the bank. Therefore, the influence of LLP on ROE in banking also depends on the wise use of reserves and the credit risk conditions faced by the bank. Banks need to ensure that reserves through LLP are sufficient to handle the credit risks faced and increase company profits in a sustainable manner to increase ROE.

(14) Ratio to Deposits. The Ratio to Deposit measures how many loans are disbursed by the bank in relation to the amount of funds received from customers. LLP can affect the Ratio to Deposit in banking because reserves created through LLP can reduce the amount of loans disbursed by the bank. LLPs can also influence customer confidence in banks, because reserves through LLPs indicate that the bank has sufficient resilience to handle credit risks. If customers feel trust in the bank, then customers may be more inclined to place their funds in the bank, thereby increasing the amount of funds received by the bank. However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank may not be able to handle credit risks well and customer confidence in the bank may decline. This can affect the Ratio to Deposit at bank.

(15) Equity ratio. The Equity Ratio measures how large a bank's own capital is in relation to the bank's total assets. LLP can affect the Equity Ratio in banking because reserves created through LLP are considered part of the bank's own capital. If the bank has sufficient reserves through LLP, then these reserves can increase the bank's Equity Ratio. This shows that the bank has sufficient capital to handle credit risks and has good resilience to face unexpected situations. However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank's Equity Ratio may decrease. This suggests that banks may not have sufficient capital to handle credit risks and have poor resilience to deal with unexpected situations. Therefore, the influence of LLP on the Equity Ratio in banking depends on the wise use of reserves and the credit risk conditions faced by the bank. Banks need to ensure that reserves through LLP are sufficient to handle the credit risks faced and increase the Equity Ratio in a sustainable manner to maintain customer trust and face unexpected situations.

(16) Market loan interest rates. Market loan interest rates are influenced by a number of factors, including the rate of inflation, Central Bank interest rates, and demand and supply of loans. LLP can influence market loan interest rates in banks because LLP can influence the credit risk faced by banks. LLPs increase the reserves created by banks to address credit risks, thereby increasing investor confidence and reducing the risk of bank bankruptcy. This can reduce the risk borne by investors, thereby increasing investor confidence and reducing market loan interest rates.

However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through the LLP to handle credit risk, then the credit risk borne by investors may increase. This can increase market lending rates because investors require additional compensation to bear the higher risk.

(17) Bank size. Bank size can be measured by total bank assets. LLP can influence the size of the bank in banking because LLP can influence the bank's financial performance. If the bank has sufficient reserves through LLP, then the bank can handle credit risks better and increase investor confidence in the bank. This can improve the bank's financial performance and increase the size of the bank. However, if the bank does not have sufficient reserves through LLP, the credit risk faced by the bank may increase, thereby reducing the bank's financial performance and reducing the size of the bank. Therefore, the impact of LLP on market lending rates and bank size on banking depends on the wise use of reserves through LLP and the credit risk conditions faced by the bank. Banks need to ensure that reserves through LLPs are sufficient to handle the credit risks they face, improve the bank's financial performance, and maintain investor confidence.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding Determinant Variables of Loan Loss Provision (LLP) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 10 determinant variables for LLP in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. The effect of CAR on Loan Loss Provision (LLP) is positive. The higher a bank's CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear credit risk. This can reduce the risk of the bank experiencing losses due to non-performing loans and ultimately reduce the LLP that needs to be formed to cover these losses. Therefore, banks with high CARs tend to have lower LLPs.

(2) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. The influence of DER on LLP in banking can vary. If a bank's DER is too high, the bank may experience difficulty in paying back its debt when it is due and may experience overall financial difficulties. This can increase the bank's risk of experiencing losses due to non-performing loans and increase the number of LLPs that need to be formed. Therefore, banks with low DER tend to have lower LLP.

(3) Good Corporate Governance/GCG. GCG is a set of company management rules and practices that prioritize transparency, accountability, fairness and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. Good GCG implementation can minimize the risk of management failure in managing credit risk and improve bank credit quality. This can affect LLP in banking, where banks that implement GCG well tend to have lower LLP levels.

(4) Governance Mechanics. Governance Mechanisms are a set of internal regulatory mechanisms or procedures that aim to ensure that a company operates effectively and in accordance with GCG principles. An effective regulatory mechanism can help banks identify and manage credit risks well, thereby minimizing the risk of default and improving credit quality. The implementation of good regulatory mechanisms can influence LLP in banking, where banks that implement effective regulatory mechanisms tend to have lower LLP levels.

(5) Income Smoothing. Income smoothing is an accounting practice used by companies to reduce profit fluctuations. This practice is carried out by moving income or costs from one period to another to balance the company's profits. Income smoothing practices carried out unethically can cause distortions in financial reports and ignore actual credit risks. This can affect LLP in banking, where unethical income smoothing practices can cause banks to show credit quality that is better than it actually is, thereby reducing the allocation of funds to LLP.

(6) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. LDR is a ratio that measures the size of loans provided by banks compared to the amount of third party funds collected. The higher

the LDR of a bank, the greater the credit risk that the bank must face. This can affect LLP in banking, where banks with high LDR tend to have a higher level of default risk, thus requiring a larger allocation of funds for LLP.

(7) Earnings management. Earnings management is an accounting practice carried out by companies to influence profits and minimize profit fluctuations. Earnings management practices can be carried out in various ways, such as moving income or costs from one period to another, changing cost or income estimates, or changing accounting policies. However, if done unethically, earnings management practices can cause distortions in financial statements and ignore true credit risks. This can affect LLPs in banking, where unethical earnings management practices can cause banks to show credit quality that is better than it actually is, thereby reducing the allocation of funds to LLPs.

(8) Non Performing Loans/NPL. NPL is credit that cannot be collected because the debtor is unable to pay or has defaulted. The higher a bank's NPL, the greater the credit risk the bank must face. This can affect LLP in banking, where banks with high NPL levels tend to have a higher level of default risk, thus requiring a larger allocation of funds for LLP.

(9) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA can influence LLP in banking because the ROA level shows how effective the bank is in utilizing the assets it owns to generate profits. If ROA is high, it means that banking is effective in generating profits and can allocate larger funds to LLP. However, if ROA is low, banks may experience difficulty in allocating funds to LLP because the profits generated from the assets held are too small.

(10) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE can influence LLP in banking because the ROE level shows how much profit the company generates from the capital it has. If ROE is high, it means the company is able to generate large profits and can allocate larger funds to LLP. However, if the ROE is low, the company may have difficulty allocating funds to LLP because the profits generated are too small.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on the mapping of the number of research publications regarding the determinants and influence of Loan Loss Provisions (LLP) on Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 1988 to 2023 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 137 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the LLP ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 10 clusters and 52 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 11 topics, cluster 2 consists of 9 topics, cluster 3 consists of 8 topics, cluster 4 consists of 6 topics, cluster 5 consists of 5 topics, cluster 6 consists of 4 topics, cluster 7 consists of 3 topics, cluster 8 consists of 3 topics, cluster 9 consists of 2 topics, and cluster 10 consists of 1 topic. Third, based on mapping literature review studies, there are 17 topics related to the influence of the LLP ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, inflation, crisis, Non-Performing Loans/NPL, Non-Performing Financing/NPF, Mudharabah financing, income before tax, non-interest income, Price Earning to Growth/PEG Ratio, risk, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Ratio to Deposit, equity ratio, market loan interest rates, and bank size. Fourth, based on a literature review, there are 10 topics related to the determinants of LLP ratios in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, Governance Mechanisms, Income Smoothing, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, earnings management, Non Performing Loans/NPL, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE.

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